

The Relationship Between Teacher Personality Types, Students' Mental Resilience and Social-Emotional Learning (SEL)

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ABSTRACT: The current study examines the relationship between teacher personality types, mental resilience, and social-emotional learning (SEL) among students within the Arab education system in Israel. Additionally, the study explores demographic differences (gender, tenure, educational background, school grade level) among teachers concerning their perceptions of mental resilience and SEL. A quantitative correlational study was conducted with a sample of 480 Arab teachers from public schools in northern Israel. Teacher personality types were assessed using the Big Five personality model, which includes types such as openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism.

The findings indicate significant positive correlations between extraversion and conscientiousness and both student resilience and SEL. Extraverted teachers, characterized by their sociable and dynamic communication styles, created supportive and engaging learning environments that enhanced student resilience. Additionally, teachers who exhibited high levels of conscientiousness provided structured and stable classroom settings, allowing students to develop effective coping skills in response to challenges. No significant demographic differences were identified in teachers' perceptions of their effectiveness in fostering resilience and SEL among students.

The study's findings highlight the importance of focusing on professional development to enhance desirable personality types among educators and the integration of culturally relevant SEL programs. In conclusion, this research emphasizes the critical role of teacher personality in shaping student outcomes related to resilience and social-emotional competencies. Recommendations include creating supportive and collaborative school environments, prioritizing teacher training that develops extraversion and conscientiousness, and fostering partnerships with community stakeholders to enhance SEL implementation.

Keywords: Teacher personality types, Mental resilience, Social emotional learning (SEL), Arab education system, culturally relevant education

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1. Introduction

In the field of educational psychology, much emphasis is placed on understanding the myriad factors that influence student development and learning outcomes. As the educational landscape becomes increasingly complex, recognizing the role of individual differences among educators has become paramount for fostering student success.

Notably, teacher personality types, particularly those articulated in the Big Five personality model, have garnered significant attention due to their potential impact on the classroom environment and student experiences.

The Big Five personality model categorizes personality into five core dimensions: Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism (Afdal et al., 2023; Yudistiro & Hadi, 2023). Each of these types influences teaching styles, classroom management, and interpersonal interactions in unique ways, which can subsequently affect student engagement, motivation, and overall learning outcomes. For instance, extraverted teachers are likely to create vibrant, interactive classrooms that stimulate student participation, while conscientious teachers provide a structured learning environment that emphasizes consistency and responsibility.

Moreover, the significance of mental resilience and social-emotional learning (SEL) in students' academic and personal success cannot be overstated. As students navigate various challenges—including academic pressures, social issues, and personal crises—resilience becomes a crucial aspect of their ability to cope and thrive. Resilience is defined as the capacity to maintain or regain psychological well-being in the face of adversity. Social-emotional learning involves processes through which students acquire the skills and competencies needed to understand and manage their emotions, set and achieve goals, demonstrate empathy, and establish healthy relationships (Bediako et al., 2023; Toirjonovich, 2023).

Given the increasing focus on holistic educational practices, investigating the relationship between teacher personality types and students' mental resilience and SEL presents a vital area for exploration. This is particularly pertinent in the Arab community in Israel, where cultural traditions and values shape educational practices and teacher-student interactions. In this context, teachers are tasked not only with delivering academic content but also with nurturing their students' social and emotional development. The interplay between teacher personality types and students' resilience and SEL is influenced by cultural norms prioritizing community relationships and familial bonds.

Thus, the central research question emerges: How do teacher personality types impact students' mental resilience and social-emotional learning within the context of Arab society in Israel? This study aims to fill the existing gap by offering insights into how these dynamics inform educational strategies, ultimately providing recommendations for culturally responsive teacher training and development. By understanding the influence of teacher personality types on student outcomes, this research aspires to contribute to the advancement of inclusive, effective, and culturally sensitive educational practices that enhance both academic and emotional experiences for students.

2. Literature Review

Teacher Personality Types: The Big Five

"Teacher personality types" refer to categories based on dominant personality types, often analyzed through the Big Five personality model. The model encompasses five main

types: Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism. Understanding these types can elucidate how they affect a teacher's behavior, interaction style, and teaching methodology, ultimately impacting their effectiveness and influence on student learning and development (Burić et al., 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023).

Openness to Experience: Openness to Experience is characterized by creativity, intellectual curiosity, and a willingness to engage with new ideas. Teachers exhibiting high levels of openness often implement innovative teaching methods and diverse instructional strategies, which can foster an enriching classroom environment (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023). They are more likely to experiment with new curricula, integrate interdisciplinary approaches, and welcome student input in the learning process. This flexibility can promote an inclusive atmosphere where students feel empowered to express their thoughts and explore new concepts without fear of judgment. Research has shown that teachers with high openness tend to be more adaptive, capable of accommodating various learning styles and needs. This adaptability not only engages students but also encourages them to develop a growth mindset, viewing challenges as opportunities for development rather than obstacles (Sung & Kim, 2023). The environment fostered by open teachers can be crucial in enhancing students' social-emotional skills, allowing them to learn empathy and collaboration through diverse activities.

Conscientiousness: Conscientiousness refers to an individual's reliability, organization, and work ethic. Teachers who are high in conscientiousness are typically thorough, dependable, and committed to their students' academic success (Burić et al., 2023; Syahrul et al., 2024). These educators excel in lesson planning and classroom management, establishing clear expectations and consistency in their teaching. The structured environment created by conscientious teachers fosters safety and confidence among students, enhancing their ability to engage with academic content effectively.

Moreover, conscientious teachers provide deliberate and consistent feedback to students, helping them recognize their strengths and weaknesses. This constructive feedback is integral to developing resilience in students, allowing them to navigate challenges and improve over time (Kellam, 2024; Rimantas & Iskakova, 2023). As such, conscientiousness not only directly influences students' academic performance but also supports their social-emotional growth, facilitating skill development in managing emotions and stress.

Extraversion: Extraversion is characterized by high energy, positive emotions, and sociability. Extraverted teachers tend to create dynamic, interactive classrooms that encourage active participation and collaboration (Burić et al., 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023). Through engaging teaching methods and enthusiastic delivery, they foster a learning environment that motivates students to participate fully and express themselves openly. The connections built by extraverted teachers are crucial in supporting students' social and emotional needs. A positive, interactive classroom atmosphere cultivates trust and fosters relationships, enabling students to feel comfortable sharing their thoughts and emotions. This connection is vital for effective SEL implementation, as students are more likely to engage in social learning when they feel supported by their educators (Afdal et al., 2023; Ananda, 2023).

Agreeableness: Agreeableness encompasses types such as empathy, kindness, and cooperation. Teachers' high in agreeableness are typically supportive and nurturing, facilitating a compassionate classroom environment that encourages emotional expression and student collaboration (DeYoung, 2024; Sarkar & Dutta, 2024). These types foster positive teacher-student relationships, which are essential for creating a safe and engaging learning atmosphere. Research indicates that agreeable teachers are more likely to promote prosocial behaviors, encouraging students to support one another and cultivate strong interpersonal skills (Bediako et al., 2023; Burić et al., 2023). By modeling understanding and teamwork, these teachers significantly impact students' emotional adjustment and resilience, helping them develop the social skills necessary for navigating personal and academic challenges.

Neuroticism: Neuroticism, often considered the inverse of emotional stability, pertains to an individual's tendency to experience negative emotions such as anxiety, anger, or sadness. Teachers with high neuroticism may struggle to maintain a calm and supportive classroom environment, potentially undermining their effectiveness in fostering student resilience and SEL (Embacher et al., 2023; Samfira et al., 2023).

Highly neurotic teachers might inadvertently project their stress and emotional instability onto their students, hindering the development of a positive learning atmosphere. Consequently, the emotional states of these teachers can impede their ability to effectively model resilience and emotional regulation, crucial components of SEL learning. Therefore, promoting emotional stability in teachers is essential for creating environments where students can thrive.

Understanding teacher personality types through the lens of the Big Five model reveals the multifaceted influences on educational practices. Genetic predispositions play a foundational role in shaping personality types, as research suggests heredity contributes to variability in characteristics like extraversion, neuroticism, and agreeableness (Husein, 2023; Rosen et al., 2023). Environmental influences also significantly shape personality types throughout an individual's life. Early familial environments, including parental styles and emotional climates, impact the development of types such as conscientiousness and agreeableness. Supportive parenting has been linked to higher levels of conscientiousness, demonstrating the importance of home environments (Li et al., 2024; Rakhmah et al., 2024).

In the Arab context, teacher personality types are shaped significantly by societal factors. Cultural values emphasize community relationships, family involvement, and social expectations, influencing how teachers express and develop their personality types. Types like agreeableness and conscientiousness are often highly regarded, reinforcing the role of teachers as community role models (Al-Hadadi, 2021; Al-Sisi, 2019). Teachers in Arab societies are expected to be compassionate and supportive while also effectively managing classroom behavior. The existing educational structure often promotes conscientiousness through the rigorous demands placed on teachers to prepare students for exams and navigate cultural expectations for respect and harmony (Mayan, 2019; Miaari, 2013).

Implications of Teacher Personality

Teacher personality types significantly influence their professional effectiveness and interactions with students. High openness allows educators to embrace diverse educational philosophies, enriching classroom experiences (Munadi & Nurulhaq, 2023; Prayitno & Ismira, 2023). Conscientious teachers maintain high organization and reliability, enhancing their reputation and student achievement. Extraverted teachers create vibrant learning environments that engage students and promote strong relationships, essential for emotional support (Afdal et al., 2023; Ananda, 2023). Emotional stability also helps teachers navigate routine challenges in effective classroom management, modeling resilience for their students (Rosen et al., 2023; Samfira et al., 2023). In recognizing these dynamics, educational institutions can create tailored interventions that foster more inclusive and supportive learning environments.

Mental Resilience

Resilience among students refers to their capacity to cope with stressors and adapt to challenges in educational settings and life. This concept encompasses the ability to maintain psychological well-being despite distress from academic pressures and personal issues (Sarkar & Dutta, 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023). Resilient students "bounce back" from setbacks, demonstrating persistence, motivation, and effective coping strategies that help mitigate stress.

Resilience can be categorized into several types: emotional resilience, social resilience, academic resilience, and mental resilience. Each type plays a critical role in helping students navigate inherent challenges in educational settings and personal development (Bediako et al., 2023; Toirjonovich, 2023): Emotional Resilience allows students to manage emotional responses to setbacks. Emotionally resilient students utilize coping strategies to handle disappointment and anxiety, maintaining a positive outlook even under stress (Ünaldı et al., 2024; Yudistiro & Hadi, 2023). Social Resilience involves maintaining relationships during periods of change. Socially resilient students seek support from peers and educators while contributing positively to their communities (Ananda, 2023; Ünaldı et al., 2024). Academic Resilience focuses on students' ability to persist in educational endeavors despite challenges. Students exhibiting strong academic resilience view obstacles as opportunities for growth rather than roadblocks (Liaqat et al., 2023; Macovei et al., 2023). Mental resilience encompasses mental fortitude, enabling students to withstand psychological stress through cognitive processes such as positive thinking and effective problem-solving (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023).

Students' mental resilience results from a complex interplay of personal, familial, and environmental factors. At the individual level, types such as optimism and adaptability enhance resilience significantly (Burić et al., 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023). Positive parental involvement and supportive family environments create essential foundations for developing resilience (Dallasheh, 2024; Rosen et al., 2023).

Educational environments that provide support—through counseling services and peer programs—also positively contribute to resilience development (Li et al., 2024; Rakhmah et al., 2024). Furthermore, positive interactions with peers strengthen resilience

by providing emotional support that buffers stress (Rakhmah et al., 2024; Rimantas & Iskakova, 2023).

Mental resilience significantly impacts academic success, affecting how students cope with stressors and enhancing learning experiences. Resilience empowers students to engage effectively in their educational pursuits, leading to sustained achievement and personal growth (Macovei et al., 2023; Qamar, 2023). Resilient students are better equipped to confront challenges, reframe setbacks, and leverage feedback for improvement (Malisi et al., 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024). Moreover, mental resilience fosters effective time management and prioritization skills, enabling students to balance commitments and improve productivity. The development of a growth mindset is another key outcome associated with resilience. Students who embrace the notion that intelligence and skills can be developed through effort tend to explore new ideas and take intellectual risks (Prayitno & Ismira, 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024). Additionally, resilience aids in emotional regulation during stress, allowing students to maintain focus during assessments and projects, thus reducing anxiety that could hinder performance (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023).

Social implications of mental resilience significantly influence students' interpersonal relationships within and beyond school. Resilient students are typically equipped with emotional tools to navigate complex social dynamics, contributing to healthier environments and a sense of belonging (Bediako et al., 2023; Burić et al., 2023). These students exhibit strong interpersonal skills essential for building effective relationships. They demonstrate effective communication, empathy, and conflict resolution, fostering positive friendships and supportive interpersonal networks (Burić et al., 2024; DeYoung, 2024). In addition, resilience in students aids better emotional regulation, crucial for managing social interactions. Students demonstrating resilience are adept at managing their impulses, preventing conflicts from escalating, and enhancing overall classroom harmony (Rosen et al., 2023; Samfira et al., 2023).

Moreover, students with resilience often serve as role models, inspiring their peers through positivity and commitment to collective goals. This dynamic promotes a supportive environment crucial for social integration and overall student morale (Embacher et al., 2023; Husein, 2023).

Mental resilience plays a pivotal role in various aspects of student life, enhancing academic performance and social skills. Schools that prioritize resilience not only prepare students for academic challenges but also equip them to engage productively in social contexts. Incorporating resilience training and support within educational programs can cultivate well-rounded individuals capable of contributing positively to society (Malisi et al., 2023; Munadi & Nurulhaq, 2023).

Grasping the multifaceted nature of mental resilience is crucial for crafting effective interventions that enable students to navigate both academic pressures and complex interpersonal relationships successfully.

Social Emotional Learning (SEL)

Social Emotional Learning (SEL) is a vital educational discipline encompassing the processes through which children and adolescents acquire the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary to understand and manage emotions, set and achieve positive goals, and maintain positive relationships. This holistic approach integrates emotional intelligence with interpersonal skills within a supportive educational framework (Bediako et al., 2023; Toirjonovich, 2023). SEL is grounded in the understanding that optimal learning occurs within supportive relationships that make educational experiences both challenging and engaging. It serves as a foundation for developing social-emotional skills that are crucial for being a responsible student, citizen, and worker. Research indicates that integrated efforts to develop students' social-emotional skills can effectively prevent risky behaviors such as drug use, bullying, and dropout rates (Ünaldı et al., 2024; Yudistiro & Hadi, 2023).

SEL incorporates five key competencies: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making, each focusing on different facets of emotional and social growth (Burić et al., 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023).

1. **Self-Awareness:** Involves understanding one's emotions, personal values, and strengths. High self-awareness empowers students to make informed choices based on a clear understanding of themselves (Ananda, 2023; Ünaldı et al., 2024).

2. **Self-Management:** This emphasizes the ability to regulate emotions and behaviors effectively. Teaching students strategies for managing stress and controlling impulses is essential for achieving personal and academic objectives (Rakhmah et al., 2024; Rimantas & Iskakova, 2023).

3. **Social Awareness:** Involves empathizing with others and recognizing social norms. SEL programs that increase social awareness help students appreciate diverse perspectives, fostering tolerance and respect (Liaqat et al., 2023; Macovei et al., 2023).

4. **Relationship Skills:** Focus on establishing and maintaining healthy relationships. Skills such as effective communication and conflict resolution are essential for creating supportive social networks (Macovei et al., 2023; Qamar, 2023).

5. **Responsible Decision-Making:** Encourages students to evaluate the consequences of their actions and make choices aligning with ethical standards and social norms. This competency is vital for making informed, constructive decisions in daily life (Malisi et al., 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024).

Integrating these competencies into educational settings equips students with a comprehensive toolkit for social and emotional development, ensuring they not only excel academically but also grow into compassionate and self-aware individuals (Prayitno & Ismira, 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024).

The effectiveness of SEL is influenced by multiple factors, which significantly affect how students acquire and apply SEL skills. These factors can be categorized into individual characteristics, family environment, school climate, and broader societal influences (Munadi & Nurulhaq, 2023; Prayitno & Ismira, 2023). Individual Factors: Types such as empathy,

openness, and emotional health impact student engagement in SEL programs. Those with strong cognitive skills can better understand complex social-emotional concepts, while students dealing with emotional distress may require more support to benefit fully from SEL (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023).

Family Environment: Nurturing families foster SEL by modeling positive interactions and providing safe spaces for emotional expression. Parental involvement significantly enhances SEL effectiveness (Qamar, 2023; Radnawati, 2023). Conversely, unstable home environments can diminish the reinforcement of SEL principles, impairing skill development. **School Environment:** The commitment of schools to SEL greatly influences its successful implementation. Institutions prioritizing SEL create integrated environments that foster students' social-emotional development (Sarkar & Dutta, 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023). Comprehensive, regularly updated SEL programs are essential to ensure relevance to students' needs. **Societal Influences:** Community norms, cultural values, and social policies shape SEL. Communities that value interpersonal relationships reinforce SEL concepts, enabling students to find relevance in their learning (Afdal et al., 2023; Yudistiro & Hadi, 2023). Policies supporting mental health and educational funding are crucial.

The implications of SEL are extensive, influencing many aspects of students' lives, including academic performance and personal relationships. As educational stakeholders increasingly recognize the importance of holistic development, SEL has become a vital component. Research indicates that students engaged in SEL programs show improved behavior, better stress management, and more positive attitudes toward their education (Ananda, 2023; Ünalı et al., 2024). Furthermore, SEL fosters healthier social interactions. Students equipped with SEL skills can better manage emotions, communicate effectively, and resolve conflicts, leading to stronger relationships with both peers and adults (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023). Healthy relationships enhance students' emotional health and solidify their sense of belonging within the school community, correlating with decreased absenteeism and disciplinary problems.

In conclusion, the integration of SEL into educational curricula substantially enriches students' academic and personal development, equipping them with the critical skills necessary for success (Embacher et al., 2023; Samfira et al., 2023). As educational institutions continue to emphasize the need for effective SEL, understanding these dynamics will inform strategies that maximize student benefit and contribute to a supportive educational experience that prepares them for future challenges.

Interactions Between Teacher Personality Types, Student Resilience and SEL

The relationship between teacher personality types, as outlined by the Big Five model, and student resilience and SEL is a compelling area of educational psychology. This connection highlights how teachers profoundly impact their students, both academically and emotionally. Teacher personality types influence teaching styles, student interactions, and classroom environments—all critically affecting students' resilience and SEL development (Li et al., 2024; Rakhmah et al., 2024).

Teachers exhibiting high levels of conscientiousness can create structured and organized learning environments. This orderliness facilitates smooth classroom operations,

providing a stable and predictable setting that promotes effective learning (Liaqat et al., 2023; Radnawati, 2023). Such environments may help mitigate student anxiety and stress, which often pose barriers to resilience. Moreover, conscientious teachers are generally dependable, cultivating a sense of security and trust among students that supports their emotional well-being (Levy-Feldman, 2020; Rimantas & Iskakova, 2023).

Teachers with high openness to experience tend to incorporate innovative methods and diverse content into their curricula. This trait stimulates intellectual curiosity and fosters a love of learning essential for promoting mental resilience. Exposure to various perspectives not only enhances resilience but helps students cultivate flexibility in thought, a critical element in adapting to new situations (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023).

Extraversion significantly influences teachers' communication abilities. In cultures that prioritize personal relationships, extraverted teachers often establish strong connections with students, which are essential for promoting both mental resilience and SEL (Al-Hadadi, 2021; Al-Sisi, 2019). The positive relationships nurtured by these teachers can significantly enhance students' social support networks, which are crucial for resilience development. The enthusiasm of extraverted teachers can further motivate students, fostering engagement and peer collaboration, which play critical roles in overcoming academic and personal challenges (Afdal et al., 2023; Ananda, 2023).

Agreeableness is a critical trait for fostering SEL, as educators characterized by empathy, kindness, and cooperation are more successful in creating supportive classroom climates. These teachers encourage students to express themselves, facilitating healthy emotional exploration and prosocial behaviors (Bediako et al., 2023; Burić et al., 2023).

Similarly, emotional stability or low neuroticism fosters a calm classroom environment. Teachers who demonstrate emotional stability handle classroom stress effectively, modeling resilience for their students. Their ability to remain composed in challenging situations enables them to instill confidence in students, teaching them that challenges are manageable (Burić et al., 2024; DeYoung, 2024).

In Conclusion, the relationship between teacher personality types and students' mental resilience and SEL within Arab society is complex and intertwined with cultural values. Acknowledging and leveraging these personality types can help develop effective teaching strategies that align with cultural expectations, promoting students' holistic development and preparing them for academic and social challenges.

In light of the above, the following research questions and hypotheses emerge from the literature review:

Research Questions

- Is there a relationship between teacher personality types, students' mental resilience and SEL from teachers' perspectives?

- Are there demographic differences (gender, tenure, educational background, school grade level) between teachers concerning their perceptions of mental resilience and SEL?

Research Hypotheses

- There is a significant relationship between teacher personality types and students' mental resilience.
- There is a significant relationship between teacher personality types and students' SEL.
- There is a significant relationship between teacher personality types (Extraversion, Neuroticism, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Openness) and mental resilience and between SEL components.
- There are demographic differences (gender, tenure, educational background, school grade level) among teachers in personality types, perceptions of mental resilience, and SEL.

3. Methodology

Research Method

A quantitative research approach is employed in this study due to its effectiveness in quantifying relationships and testing hypotheses through statistical methods. The hypotheses focus on establishing clear links between teacher personality types and student outcomes related to mental resilience and social-emotional learning (SEL). This structured approach allows for numerical analysis of variables, which is appropriate for examining the relationships between teacher personality and student resilience as well as SEL. Moreover, quantitative research facilitates demographic comparisons among teachers, enabling statistical evaluation of how factors such as gender, tenure, and education influence perceptions and effectiveness in educational practices (Claro et al., 2024).

Population and Sample

The research population consists of Arab teachers in northern Israel working in public schools. The sample includes 480 Arab teachers from two public schools, selected through convenience sampling. This method is advantageous for its cost-effectiveness and ease of access to willing participants, making it suitable when the focus is on gaining general insights into specific phenomena rather than achieving broader generalizations. The demographic characteristics of the study participants are detailed in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Demographic Data

Variables and Categories	N (%) / M ± SD
Gender	
Male	180 (37.5%)
Female	300 (62.5%)
Age (range 28-55 years)	M = 40.16, SD = 8.19
Tenure (range 1-31 years)	M = 14.65, SD = 8.29
Track	
Elementary	160 (33.3%)
Middle School	172 (35.8%)
High School	148 (30.8%)
Specialization	
Humanities	292 (60.8%)
Sciences	188 (39.2%)
Position	
Educator	352 (73.3%)
Coordinator	100 (20.8%)
Administration	28(5.8%)
Education	
Bachelor's Degree	208 (43.3%)
Master's Degree	272 (56.7%)
Religion	
Muslim	368 (76.7%)
Christian	96 (20%)
Druze	16 (3.3%)

□

Table 1 provides an overview of the demographic characteristics of the study's participants, consisting of 480 Arab teachers from public schools in northern Israel. The sample includes a higher proportion of females (62.5%) compared to males (37.5%), with ages ranging from 28 to 55 years ($M = 40.16$, $SD = 8.19$). In terms of tenure, participants have between 1 and 31 years of experience ($M = 14.65$, $SD = 8.29$). The distribution across educational tracks shows 33.3% in elementary, 35.8% in middle school, and 30.8% in high school. Specializations among participants include 60.8% in humanities and 39.2% in sciences. Regarding their roles, 73.3% are educators, 20.8% are coordinators, and 5.8% are in administration. Educationally, 43.3% hold a bachelor's degree and 56.7% a master's degree. The religious distribution includes 76.7% Muslim, 20% Christian, and 3.3% Druze. This demographic data highlights the diversity within the teaching staff, offering insights into the varied experiences and educational settings of the participants.

Table 2: Distribution of the Study Population by Personality Types

Personality Type	M (%)	SD
Extraversion	3.61 (28%)	0.95
Neuroticism	2.52 (12%)	0.55
Agreeableness	3.46 (22%)	1.13
Conscientiousness	3.57 (30%)	0.95
Openness	3.48 (8%)	1.09

Table 2 summarizes the distribution of personality types among the study population using the Big Five model. Extraversion (mean = 3.61, 28%) and conscientiousness (mean = 3.57, 30%) are the most prevalent types, highlighting sociability and reliability within the group. Agreeableness scores a mean of 3.46 (22%), indicating moderate levels of kindness and cooperation. Neuroticism, with a mean of 2.52 (12%), reflects lower emotional instability, while openness at 3.48 (8%) suggests some creativity and willingness to embrace new experiences.

Research Instruments

This study utilized 4 research instruments for data collection:

1. **Demographic Questionnaire:** This includes questions regarding gender, age, tenure, educational track, teaching specialization, teaching subject, position, education level, teaching experience, and ethnic-religious background (Appendix 1).
2. **Mental Resilience Questionnaire:** Comprising 50 items rated on a scale from 1 to 4, where 1 indicates lack of resilience and 4 indicates strong agreement with resilience-related statements. The reliability of the questionnaire is $\alpha = .925$ (Appendix 2).

3. SEL Questionnaire: The Teacher Attitudes about Social and Emotional Learning (TASEL) assesses teachers' attitudes towards SEL, including four parts (general attitudes, training, program implementation, program contribution). Responses are rated from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree), with an overall reliability of $\alpha = .846$ (Appendix 3).

4. Big Five Personality Questionnaire: This assessment evaluates teacher personality across five types—extraversion, neuroticism, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness. The questionnaire consists of 44 items, rated on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Reliability scores for each personality trait range from $\alpha = .68$ to $\alpha = .951$ (Appendix 4).

Research Procedure

Data collection was conducted using Google Forms, a user-friendly tool for gathering survey data. This platform allows for the creation of structured questionnaires essential for capturing the quantitative data necessary to test the research hypotheses. Its accessibility enables researchers to distribute and collect responses efficiently, especially useful given the geographical distribution of participants in northern Israel. Google Forms supports real-time data collection and organization, streamlining the analysis process.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data analysis process involves several stages, starting with coding and preparing the data collected through Google Forms to ensure accuracy and completeness. Descriptive statistics summarize the sample's demographic characteristics, and the distribution of responses related to teacher personality, mental resilience, and SEL. Inferential statistics, including correlation and regression analyses, explore the relationships between teacher personality types and SEL, providing empirical support for the research hypotheses. The analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 29, which facilitates sophisticated data analysis and interpretation of complex datasets.

Research Ethics

Maintaining ethical standards in this research is crucial to protect the rights and dignity of participants. Informed consent is obtained by clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participants are informed that their involvement is voluntary and that they may withdraw at any time without penalties. Privacy and confidentiality are prioritized; data collected via Google Forms is anonymous to preclude personal identification, with results reported only in aggregate. To address cultural sensitivities, the research protocol was designed in consultation with Arabic educational leaders, ensuring cultural competency and relevance. This approach not only enhances the ethical integrity of the research but also supports its acceptance within the community, bolstering the reliability of the findings.

4. Findings

The objective of the current study is to examine the relationship between teacher personality types and student mental resilience and Social Emotional Learning (SEL). To achieve this, a quantitative correlational study was conducted, involving 480 teachers selected through convenience sampling. The findings of the study are presented below. To examine the first three hypotheses, a Pearson correlation was conducted, with the results shown in the correlation matrix in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	M	SD	Cronbach's α	Extraversion	Neuroticism	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Openness	Resilience	Attitudes Toward SEL	SEL Training	SEL Implementation	SEL Contribution
Extraversion	3.61	0.95	0.776	1									
Neuroticism	2.52	0.55	0.777	0.14	1								
Agreeableness	3.46	1.13	0.951	0.04	0.15	1							
Conscientiousness	3.57	0.95	0.780	0.71***	0.01	0.03	1						
Openness	3.48	1.09	0.950	0.01	0.12	0.02	0.03	1					
Resilience	2.90	0.51	0.925	0.73***	0.03	0.00	0.79***	0.02	1				
Attitudes Toward Social-Emotional Learning	3.53	0.95	0.878	0.62***	-0.03	-0.04	0.63***	0.01	0.63***	1			
SEL Training	3.58	0.93	0.889	0.71***	0.06	-0.04	0.74***	0.03	0.77***	0.58***	1		
SEL Implementation	3.49	1.01	0.874	0.42***	-0.01	-0.01	0.53***	-0.05	0.44***	0.37***	0.54***	1	
SEL Contribution	3.58	0.96	0.799	0.55***	0.06	0.01	0.55***	0.02	0.48***	0.54***	0.51***	0.36***	1
Social-Emotional Learning (Total Scale)	3.55	0.76	0.846	0.75***	0.02	-0.03	0.79***	0.01	0.76***	0.82***	0.86***	0.66***	0.76***

*** $p < .001$

Based on the Pearson correlation matrix in Table 3 above, the following hypotheses were examined:

Hypothesis 1

"There is a significant relationship between teacher personality type and students' mental resilience".

Based on Table 3, there is a strong positive significant correlation ($p < .001$) teacher personality types and between mental resilience. Thus, the first research hypothesis that states a significant relationship exists between teacher personality type and students' mental resilience is confirmed. These correlations indicate that when teachers exhibit higher levels of extraversion and conscientiousness, their students tend to demonstrate greater mental resilience.

Hypothesis 2

"There is a significant relationship between teacher personality type and students' social emotional learning".

Table 3 indicates a significant positive correlation ($p < .001$) between teacher personality type and students' social emotional learning. Thus, the second research hypothesis is confirmed. These findings indicate that teachers who exhibit higher levels of extraversion and conscientiousness positively impact their students' social-emotional development.

Hypothesis 3

There is a significant relationship between types of teacher personalities and mental resilience and between social emotional learning components.

Table 3 shows a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.73$, $p < .001$) between extraversion ($M = 3.61$, $SD = 0.95$) and resilience ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.51$); a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.79$, $p < .001$) between conscientiousness ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 0.95$) and resilience ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.51$); no significant statistical correlations ($p < .05$) between neuroticism ($M = 2.52$, $SD = 0.55$), agreeableness ($M = 3.46$, $SD = 1.13$), and openness ($M = 3.48$, $SD = 1.09$) with resilience ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.51$).

Additionally, there is a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.62$, $p < .001$) between extraversion and teachers' attitudes toward social emotional learning ($M = 3.53$, $SD = 0.95$); a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.63$; $p < .001$) between conscientiousness and teachers' attitudes toward social emotional learning; and no significant statistical correlations ($p < .05$) between neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness with teachers' attitudes toward social emotional learning.

There is also a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.71$, $p < .001$) between extraversion and teachers' SEL training ($M = 3.58$, $SD = 0.93$); a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.74$; $p < .001$) between conscientiousness and SEL training; and no significant correlations ($p < .05$) between neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness with SEL training. There is a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.42$, $p < .001$) between extraversion and teachers' SEL implementation ($M = 3.49$, $SD = 1.01$); a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.53$; $p < .001$) between conscientiousness and SEL implementation; and no significant correlations ($p < .05$) between neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness with SEL implementation. There is a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.55$, $p < .001$) between extraversion and SEL contribution in teachers' views ($M = 3.58$, $SD = 0.96$); a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.55$; $p < .001$) between conscientiousness and SEL contribution in teachers' views; and no significant correlations ($p < .05$) between neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness with SEL contribution in teachers' views.

Thus, the third research hypothesis, proposing a significant relationship between types of teacher personalities and components of resilience and social emotional learning, is only partially supported, specifically regarding the relationship between extraversion and conscientiousness with all components of the social emotional learning scale.

Hypothesis 4

"There are demographic differences (gender, tenure, educational background, school grade level) among teachers in personality types, perceptions of mental resilience,

and SEL". To examine the fourth research hypothesis, hierarchical regression was performed. The results are shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Hierarchical Regression for Examining the Relationship Between Demographic Data and Resilience and Social-Emotional Learning Among Teachers

Model 1			Model 2		
Variables	B	β	Variables	B	β
Extraversion	0.25	0.31***	Gender	0.00	0.00
Neuroticism	0.03	0.02	Tenure	0.00	-0.04
Agreeableness	-0.04	-0.06	Education	0.08	0.05
Conscientiousness	0.32	0.39***	Position	-0.04	-0.03
Openness	-0.009	-0.01	Grade Level	0.03	0.04
Resilience	0.32	0.21*	Extraversion	0.25	0.31***
			Neuroticism	0.01	0.01
			Agreeableness	-0.03	-0.05
			Conscientiousness	0.32	0.40***
			Openness	-0.01	0.03
			Resilience	0.31	0.21*

* $p < .05$ *** $p < .001$

Table 4 presents the results of a hierarchical regression analysis aimed at examining the relationship between demographic variables and the dependent variable of social-emotional learning (SEL), while also considering teacher personality types. The analysis is divided into two models:

Model 1

In Model 1, personality types are examined as the primary predictors of students' SEL. The regression coefficients (B) and standardized coefficients (β) for each personality trait are displayed. The results highlight the following key findings:

- Extraversion shows a significant positive influence on SEL with $B = 0.25$ and $\beta = 0.31^{***}$, indicating that higher extraversion in teachers is associated with more effective SEL implementation.
- Conscientiousness also has a significant positive effect ($B = 0.32$, $\beta = 0.39^{***}$), suggesting that organized and reliable teachers contribute positively to the social-emotional development of their students.
- Agreeableness was identified with a negative coefficient ($B = -0.04$, $\beta = -0.06$), indicating a non-significant relationship with SEL. This suggests that agreeableness alone does not enhance SEL significantly in this context.

- Neuroticism and Openness did not demonstrate a significant impact on SEL, reflecting that emotional instability and creative thinking, while important, do not directly correlate with effective SEL practices in the classroom.

The model indicates that both extraversion and conscientiousness are essential for promoting SEL, with a strong emphasis on their predictive value.

Model 2

Model 2 builds upon the first model by introducing demographic variables: gender, tenure, education, position, and grade level, while retaining the personality types as influential factors. Interestingly, the inclusion of demographic data does not change the significance of personality types.

- The coefficients for demographic variables (e.g., Gender: $B = 0.00$, $\beta = 0.00$; Tenure: $B = 0.00$, $\beta = -0.04$) indicate that these factors do not significantly predict students' perceptions of SEL.

- The significant predictive power of extraversion ($B = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.31^{***}$) and conscientiousness ($B = 0.32$, $\beta = 0.40^{***}$) remains consistent, emphasizing the importance of these personality types over demographic factors in shaping SEL outcomes.

The findings from Table 4 collectively underscore the primary role of intrinsic characteristics, particularly extraversion and conscientiousness, in fostering social-emotional learning among students, regardless of demographic constraints.

Table 5: Explained Variance

R²	0.722	0.730	
ΔR^2	0.722	0.008	$p > .05$

Table 5 indicates that, three variables significantly predict 73% of the explained variance in social-emotional learning (SEL): extraversion ($B = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.31$, $p < .001$), conscientiousness ($B = 0.32$, $\beta = 0.40$, $p < .001$), and resilience ($B = 0.31$, $\beta = 0.21$, $p < .05$).

5. Discussion

The current study aimed to explore the relationship between teacher personality types, mental resilience, and Social Emotional Learning (SEL) among Arab students. The findings revealed significant correlations between two teacher personality types: extraversion and conscientiousness and student resilience and SEL. Demographic factors such as gender, tenure, education, and grade level did not show significant differences in teachers' perceptions of mental resilience or SEL. Additionally, extraversion, conscientiousness, and resilience accounted for 73% of the variance in teachers' SEL.

The study found a positive correlation between extraversion teacher personality type and mental resilience, as well as between conscientiousness type and mental resilience. Extraverted teachers, who are sociable, assertive, and enthusiastic, are likely to create interactive classroom environments that promote student engagement and mental resilience. Their optimistic behavior fosters a supportive atmosphere where students are encouraged to face challenges with confidence, thus reinforcing resilience. Similarly, conscientious teachers, known for their diligence and organization, provide structured and predictable classroom environments that help students develop self-discipline and mental resilience (Afdal et al., 2023; Yudistiro & Hadi, 2023).

On the other hand, no significant relationships were found between neuroticism, agreeableness, openness, and resilience. Teachers' high in neuroticism, marked by emotional instability, may struggle to foster resilience in their students. Although agreeableness promotes positive teacher-student relationships, it may not directly contribute to resilience, which requires a more structured approach. Openness, while encouraging creativity and intellectual curiosity, does not necessarily equip teachers with the tools to develop resilience (Kellam, 2024; Rimantas & Iskakova, 2023).

In conclusion, extraversion and conscientiousness play critical roles in promoting student resilience through structured and supportive classroom environments. These types highlight the need for educational practices that consider teacher personality as a key factor in fostering resilience and SEL (Bediako et al., 2023; Toirjonovich, 2023).

The study also revealed a significant positive correlation between extraversion, conscientiousness, and teachers' attitudes toward SEL, while no significant correlations were found for neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness. Extraverted teachers are likely to view SEL positively due to their natural ability to create dynamic and interactive classroom environments. Their proactive involvement in promoting SEL is aligned with their social nature, fostering emotional intelligence and empathy in students (Ünalı et al., 2024; Yudistiro & Hadi, 2023).

Conscientious teachers' systematic and organized teaching style allows them to integrate SEL into their curriculum effectively. Their attention to detail ensures that SEL is addressed with the same rigor as academic content. These teachers provide consistent support, helping students build emotional and social skills necessary for holistic development (Ananda, 2023; Ünalı et al., 2024).

The absence of significant correlations between neuroticism, agreeableness, openness, and attitudes toward SEL suggests that these types do not influence a teacher's engagement with SEL. Teachers high in neuroticism may find it difficult to focus on SEL, as they are preoccupied with managing their emotions. Similarly, while agreeableness promotes compassionate relationships, it does not drive a structured approach to SEL implementation. Openness, while encouraging creativity, does not necessarily translate to the systematic application of SEL strategies (Liaqat et al., 2023; Macovei et al., 2023).

In summary, extraversion and conscientiousness significantly influence teachers' positive attitudes toward SEL. Educational institutions can harness these types to foster environments that prioritize students' emotional well-being and development.

Extraversion type and conscientiousness type were also positively correlated with teachers' engagement in SEL training, whereas neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness types did not show significant correlations. Extraverted teachers, with their sociable and assertive nature, are likely to engage actively in SEL training, which often involves collaborative activities. Their enthusiasm fosters a dynamic learning environment in training sessions, contributing to the development and implementation of SEL practices (Burić et al., 2023; Syahrul et al., 2024).

Conscientious teachers approach SEL training with diligence and organization, ensuring that they absorb and integrate SEL practices into their teaching routines. Their structured approach to learning allows them to apply SEL principles systematically in their classrooms. This long-term commitment to SEL training ensures that they are well-equipped to address the social and emotional needs of their students (DeYoung, 2024; Sarkar & Dutta, 2024).

In contrast, teachers with high levels of neuroticism may avoid SEL training due to emotional instability, while agreeable teachers may rely on natural empathy rather than formal training. Teachers' high in openness, while curious and creative, may prioritize other areas of professional development over SEL (Embacher et al., 2023; Samfira et al., 2023).

The study found that extraversion and conscientiousness were significantly correlated with SEL implementation by teachers, while neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness were not. Extraverted teachers naturally create engaging environments conducive to SEL. Their social nature enables them to foster strong relationships with students, which are essential for implementing SEL strategies. Students in these environments are more likely to feel safe and supported, fostering the development of emotional and social skills (Li et al., 2024; Rakhmah et al., 2024).

Conscientious teachers, with their structured and consistent teaching methods, effectively integrate SEL into the curriculum. Their planning and organizational skills ensure that SEL activities are consistently applied, creating a predictable environment that nurtures students' emotional growth (Rakhmah et al., 2024; Rimantas & Iskakova, 2023).

Neuroticism, associated with emotional instability, may hinder teachers from maintaining the emotional balance required for effective SEL implementation. Agreeable teachers may support SEL informally but may lack the systematic approach necessary for its structured implementation. Openness, while fostering creativity, does not necessarily translate to a focused implementation of SEL (Liaqat et al., 2023; Radnawati, 2023).

Extraversion and conscientiousness were positively correlated with teachers' perceptions of SEL's contributions to student development. Extraverted teachers, due to their active engagement with students and the curriculum, are likely to perceive SEL as a significant contributor to student growth. Their enthusiasm for fostering emotional intelligence and empathy aligns with SEL's core goals, enhancing the perceived value of SEL (Prayitno & Ismira, 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024).

Similarly, conscientious teachers, with their structured and reliable approach, see SEL as integral to holistic student development. Their systematic implementation of SEL

provides consistent support for students' emotional and social growth. The careful planning and attention to detail of conscientious teachers reinforce the positive impact of SEL, making it a central aspect of the educational experience (Munadi & Nurulhaq, 2023; Prayitno & Ismira, 2023).

The lack of significant correlations between neuroticism, agreeableness, openness, and SEL perceptions may indicate that these types do not influence how teachers evaluate SEL's contributions. Teachers with high neuroticism may struggle to appreciate SEL due to emotional challenges, while agreeable and open teachers may not focus on SEL as a structured practice (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023).

Extraversion, conscientiousness, and resilience were found to predict 73% of the variance in SEL implementation, with demographic factors like gender and tenure not contributing significantly. This underscores the importance of focusing on personality types rather than demographic variables when assessing teachers' ability to implement SEL. Extraverted teachers create vibrant classroom environments, and conscientious teachers apply SEL in structured and consistent ways, both leading to improved SEL outcomes (Malisi et al., 2023; Munadi & Nurulhaq, 2023). Resilience plays a crucial role in SEL implementation, as teachers who are emotionally resilient can consistently promote SEL even when faced with challenges. This emotional strength not only benefits the teachers but also provides a model for students, fostering resilience in them as well (Prayitno & Ismira, 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024).

The study underscores the importance of intrinsic teacher personality types, specifically extraversion, conscientiousness, and resilience, in predicting the effectiveness of social-emotional learning (SEL) implementation, accounting for 73% of the variance in SEL outcomes. Unlike demographic factors such as gender, tenure, education, position, and grade level, which do not significantly affect SEL, these personality types play a critical role in shaping educational experiences. Extraversion, with its elements of sociability and enthusiasm, allows teachers to create dynamic, engaging classroom environments that foster strong interpersonal connections and encourage active student participation, thereby enhancing SEL (Malisi et al., 2023; Munadi & Nurulhaq, 2023). Conscientiousness contributes through teachers' diligence and structured teaching approaches, which systematically integrate SEL into curricula, ensuring a stable environment essential for developing social and emotional skills (Nadmilail et al., 2023; Prasetyono et al., 2023). Furthermore, resilience in teachers, characterized by emotional strength and adaptability, enables them to consistently implement SEL practices even amid challenges, inspiring students to develop their resilience and emotional capabilities (Prayitno & Ismira, 2023; Puspitasari et al., 2024). These insights suggest that educational institutions should prioritize professional development focusing on these personality types to enhance SEL effectiveness, ultimately supporting comprehensive student growth and well-being (Qamar, 2023; Radnawati, 2023; Resh & Blass, 2019; Sarkar & Dutta, 2024; Sung & Kim, 2023). By developing these types, schools can foster environments that better support students' social and emotional learning and prepare them for future challenges.

The study highlights the significant roles of extraversion, conscientiousness, and resilience in promoting SEL. These types, rather than demographic factors, are critical in

fostering environments where SEL can thrive. By recognizing the importance of these personality types, educational institutions can enhance SEL practices, ultimately benefiting students' social, emotional, and academic development (Qamar, 2023; Radnawati, 2023).

6. Conclusions

The current study highlights several key conclusions regarding the relationship between teacher personality, student outcomes, and the cultural context of Arab society in Israel. It emphasizes the significant impact of specific teacher personality traits, such as extraversion and conscientiousness, on the mental resilience and social-emotional learning (SEL) of students. These findings reaffirm the critical role teachers play in shaping the educational environment and enhancing student development.

The research underscores the importance of integrating SEL into educational curricula, as it positively influences students' emotional, social, and academic development, contributing to their overall well-being. Furthermore, the study calls for more holistic teacher training programs that focus not only on professional skills but also on developing personal attributes like extraversion and conscientiousness. This approach would foster a more engaging and structured learning environment conducive to SEL and student resilience.

In the specific context of Arab society in Israel, the study reveals that teacher personality traits must be understood within cultural frameworks that value communal ties and familial relationships. Teachers who model resilience and empathy are better equipped to inspire students to navigate the socio-economic challenges they face. Moreover, SEL programs tailored to the cultural and socio-economic realities of Arab students can help bridge existing educational gaps and provide support for their academic and emotional needs.

The research also highlights the importance of collaboration between schools and the local community, including parents and community leaders, to ensure that SEL initiatives are culturally relevant and effective. Targeted professional development for teachers in the Arab education system, focusing on traits that foster SEL and resilience, is crucial for improving student outcomes.

In conclusion, the study stresses the need for culturally aware educational strategies that recognize the diversity within the Arab community. Future research should explore the complex relationships between teacher personality, cultural values, and student outcomes to inform more effective educational interventions. This culturally sensitive approach is essential for creating supportive learning environments that nurture both academic success and emotional resilience.

Limitations of the Study

One limitation of the study is the reliance on self-reported data, which may introduce biases and affect result accuracy. Participants' perceptions and self-assessments might be influenced by subjective experiences, potentially impacting findings. Additionally, the cross-sectional design captures data at a single point in time, which may not fully explain the dynamic nature of personality types and their influence on social-emotional learning (SEL)

over time. Longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into how these relationships develop and persist. Finally, the sample may not fully represent the broader teaching population, limiting the generalizability of the results. Future research should aim for more diverse and representative samples to improve applicability in various educational contexts.

Research Recommendations

Based on the findings and limitations, future research should follow changes in teachers' personality types and their impact on SEL implementation over time. Incorporating a mixed-methods approach could enrich data by combining quantitative measures with qualitative insights, such as interviews or focus groups. Broadening the research scope to include varied educational settings and diverse teacher populations would enhance generalizability.

Furthermore, prioritizing the development of extraversion, conscientiousness, and resilience among teachers through targeted professional development programs is essential. Integrating SEL into teacher preparation programs can equip new educators with the necessary skills for promoting holistic student development. By implementing these strategies, the educational field can enhance the overall impact of SEL on students' social, emotional, and academic growth.

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